

Kinetics of Complex Formation Between Cr(III) and Phosphoric Acid

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CHROMIUM(III) ion is known to form a number of complexes with phosphoric acid¹⁻³.

pH-titration and spectro-photometric studies by Lahiri and Aditya⁴ indicated the presence of the complex

at pH's below 2 and no anionic and polynuclear complexes are formed. However, it was found that the reaction between Cr³⁺ ion and phosphoric acid is peculiarly slow.

It appears to be interesting to undertake the study of the kinetics of the complex formation between Cr(III) ion and phosphoric acid which we report in this short communication.

It was found that the reaction between Cr³⁺ ion and phosphoric acid was slow for any rate-measurement at 25° as reported by Holroyd and Salmon² and the equilibrium was not reached even after three months, but at 40°, the rate of reaction was rapid and the equilibrium was reached within one month. This temperature (40°) was selected to study the rate-measurements as at this temperature, the conversion of the purple-red uncomplexed solution into the green complexed form takes place at a reasonable rate and a radical change seemed to take place in solutions kept above this temperature.¹⁻³

Experimental

Cr(ClO₄)₃ was prepared and chromium and the free acid content of the stock solution were estimated in the same way as previously described⁴. NaClO₄ used was prepared by neutralising HClO₄ (E.P. E. Merck) acid with Na₂CO₃ (E.P. E. Merck). It was purified by recrystallising and estimated gravimetrically.

A kinetic study of the complexation reaction was made at 40° ± 0.01° and μ = 0.25 and 0.50M (adjusted by NaClO₄). A number of solutions containing different amounts of Cr(ClO₄)₃ and H₃PO₄ acid (and NaClO₄ solution) were mixed at room temperature in conical flasks and allowed to attain equilibrium at 40° and O.d. values at zero time were noted in each case.

The solutions were taken out at different time intervals and O.d. readings were taken with a Beckmann DU Spectrophotometer. The pHs of the solutions were measured with a Cambridge bench type battery operated pH-meter.

The O.d. readings at various time intervals of some typical sets are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1

Temp. = 40°		μ = 0.25M	
Cr(ClO ₄) ₃ = 0.020M,		H ₃ PO ₄ = 0.024M, d ₀ = 0.315	
		pH = 1.66	
t in hours	d _t	d _t - d ₀	$\frac{d-d_0}{t} \times 10^4$
(1) 70	0.339	0.024	3.42
(2) 98	0.354	0.039	3.98
(3) 142	0.370	0.055	3.87
(4) 219	0.395	0.080	3.65
(5) 335	0.433	0.118	3.52
(6) 407	0.455	0.140	3.44
Cr(ClO ₄) ₃ = 0.012M, H ₃ PO ₄ = 0.01M, pH = 1.80, d ₀ = 0.170			
(1) 47	0.181	0.011	2.34
(2) 94	0.192	0.022	2.34
(3) 141	0.204	0.034	2.41
(4) 215	0.219	0.049	2.28
(5) 275	0.238	0.068	2.47
(6) 333	0.246	0.076	2.28
(7) 405	0.260	0.090	2.22

Results and Discussion

Rate measurements are obviously difficult for this inert system as CrHPO₄⁺, CrOH⁺⁺, and Cr(ClO₄)₃—all absorb in the U.V. region and none of the species have got absorption maximum in this region. The absorption due to Cr(ClO₄)₃, Cr(OH)⁺⁺ and CrHPO₄⁺ complexes are strongly dependent on pH as well as temperature. Again, in acidic solutions containing a metal ion of charge +3 or larger, polymeric species are possible. Extensive studies made by King and co-workers⁵ and Poulsen, Bjerrum and Poulsen⁶ strongly indicate that at our experimental pHs (below pH 2) and at 40°, there is very little chance of polymeric species to be present. Jones and Bjerrum⁷ also found evidence of [Cr^{III}(H₂O)₅(ClO₄)₂]²⁺ complex but only in 5-10M HClO₄.

Thus, under our experimental conditions, when the concentrations of Cr(III) and H₃PO₄ are in large excess and pHs < 2, the only reactions that are of importance are

and

It is, therefore, apparent that the hydrolytic equilibrium competes with the complexation equilibrium. Actually, it has been observed that the O.d. of Cr(ClO₄)₃ is dependent on pH. It has been found that the O.d.'s of aged solutions of Cr³⁺ ion are different from the O.d.'s of the same solution of Cr³⁺ ion kept at 25°.

The pH of $Cr(ClO_4)_3$ solution diminishes as the ageing proceeds (which is quite measurable if the pH of the solution was rather high). This is probably due to the reaction

The equilibration, however, achieves completion within a short time.

The works of King and co-workers⁵ show conclusively that when the pH of the solution is low, the hydrolytic equilibrium must be small enough to be neglected. To avoid the chance of our results being vitiated by the change in O.d. values, if any, due to aging, the measurements were taken at 260 and 270 nm where the change in O.d. values due to ageing (under our experimental conditions) has been found to be very small (within experimental errors).

The amount of complex formed at various intervals of time can be determined in the same way as described before⁴. However, for the kinetic measurement in this case, we are concerned with the change $d_t - d_0$ with time. O.d. values were found to vary linearly with time. The o.d. values at different time intervals were plotted against time for each set of solution (Fig. 1) and extrapolated to zero time to have d_0 values. However, there is slight discrepancy in the O.d. values obtained at the time of mixing and the extra-polated value at zero time. The values of d_t at various time intervals at 270 nm and $\frac{d_t - d_0}{t}$ values for a number of solutions are given in Table 1. For any solution at a particular pH , it has been found that $\frac{d_t - d_0}{t}$ is a constant quantity within experimental errors. The rate of reaction

Fig. 1. Wavelength = 270 nm
Ionic strength = 0.25M

	[Cr(ClO ₄) ₃]	[H ₃ PO ₄]	pH
I.	0.006M	0.006M	1.97
II.	0.012M	0.010M	1.80
III.	0.015M	0.015M	1.73
IV.	0.020M	0.024M	1.56

has been found to be independent of the concentrations of the substance taking part in the reaction. Thus, the reaction between chromic ion and phosphoric acid is a zero-order reaction under our experimental conditions. It has been found that the equilibrium is reached in about 700 hr but the reaction in the region 500–700 hr is not a zero-order reaction. More detailed study are necessary to have a definite say regarding the order of the reaction in this region.

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Chemisorption of Nitrogen by Carbon Blacks on Treatment with Dimethylamine

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THE influence of combined oxygen in enhancing adsorption of ammonia, methylamine and other amines by carbons has been attributed either to formation of hydrogen-bonds¹ of these compounds with the constituents of oxygen complex or to their neutralization at the acidic sites on the surface provided by CO₂-complex. The possibility of chemisorption of nitrogen² in the process has not been explored. The present work describes fixation of nitrogen on treatment of sugar and coconut shell charcoals outgassed at different temperatures with dimethylamine in aqueous solution as well as gaseous state. For the reaction in solution phase, it was found convenient to mix 1 g. charcoal with 100 ml of 0.305N solution and to shake the suspension mechanically for a period of 72 hr. For the reaction in gaseous phase, dimethylamine obtained by warming aqueous solution (40%) and dried over fused